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Report on the climate suitability analysis of *Leucinodes orbonalis*

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Abstract

Climate suitability analysis allows to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest. This analysis is typically based on pest ecophysiology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available. In the context of the related EFSA pest risk assessment (PRA), a climate suitability analysis was performed for *Leucinodes orbonalis*. The current report includes: (i) the result of the extensive literature search conducted to retrieve data and information on the pest observed distribution and ecophysiology parameters, and on the methodology of the climate suitability analysis, (ii) an excel file including metadata on the literature analysed, (iii) an excel file including the observed distribution of the pest, (iv) maps related to the climate suitability analysis of *Leucinodes orbonalis*, (v) a Geopackage file including the layers related to the climate suitability analysis, and (vi) a zip folder containing the QGIS styles used to build the maps.

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Keywords: (climate suitability, pest risk assessment, pest distribution, *Leucinodes orbonalis*, Brinjal fruit borer, Eggplant fruit and shoot borer)

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1 Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). Because of this, an extensive literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the Pest Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and/or its Impact of the pest *Leucinodes orbonalis*. Then, the data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *Leucinodes orbonalis* in the EU.

2 Note on this report

This document includes a description of the methodology and results of the systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis developed in the context of the EFSA Scientific Opinion on *Leucinodes orbonalis* for the European Union (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2023). For a complete discussion of results and conclusions of the present analysis, please refer to the related Scientific Opinion cited above (currently under preparation at the time of publishing this report).

3 Methods

3.1 Systematic literature search

Searches were performed to capture the existing literature on *L. orbonalis*.

Table 1: Scientific and common names, taxonomy, EPPO code, and main hosts of *Leucinodes orbonalis*.

Scientific name	<i>Leucinodes orbonalis</i> (Guenée)
Other scientific names	<i>Pycnarmon discerptalis</i> (Hampson) ¹
International common names	Brinjal fruit borer ^{1,2} Brinjal fruit and shoot borer ¹ Eggplant fruit borer ^{1,3} Eggplant fruit and shoot borer ² Perceuse de l'aubergine ^{1,3} Foreuse des solanées ³ Auberginenfruchtbohrer ^{1,3}
Taxonomy	Kingdom: <i>Animalia</i> Phylum: <i>Arthropoda</i> Class: <i>Insecta</i> Order: <i>Lepidoptera</i> Family: <i>Crambidae</i>
EPPO code	LEUIOR
Crop hosts	<i>Solanaceae</i> , <i>Beta vulgaris</i> , <i>Capsicum annuum</i> , <i>Ipomoea batatas</i> , <i>Magnifera indica</i> , <i>Physalis minima</i> , <i>Physalis peruviana</i> , <i>Pisum sativum</i>

¹ <https://www.cabi.org/cabithesaurus/mtwdk.exe?yi=home>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

³ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

The Web of Science (All Databases) and Scopus literature databases were queried, and search results were crosschecked (and integrated if needed) with records from EPPO Global database and CABI. Only the scientific and common names of the pest, retrieved from the EPPO GD³, CABI², and CABI Thesaurus¹ (Table 1) were used to develop the search string (Table 2). No other keywords were used (e.g., "biology", "physiology", "temperature", "distribution", etc...) not to limit the retrieval of documents useful for the purposes of this search. Two additional searches were performed in Google Scholar for the international common names in French: *foreuse des solanées* and *perceur de l'aubergine*, yielding 8 and 2 scientific papers respectively.

Table 2: Search strings used, and queries results found in Web of Science and Scopus.

Platform	Date of search	Query	N of documents
Web of Science	12/12/2022	TS=("Leucinodes orbonalis" OR "Leucinodes pseudorbonalis" OR "Leucinodes" OR "Pycnarmon discerptalis" OR "eggplant fruit borer" OR "brinjal fruit borer" OR "foreuse des solanées" OR "Auberginenfruchtbohrer" OR "brinjal fruit and shoot borer" OR "eggplant fruit and shoot borer" OR "Foreuse des solanées")	1446
Scopus	12/12/2022	TITLE-ABS-KEY("Leucinodes orbonalis" OR "Leucinodes pseudorbonalis" OR "Leucinodes" OR "Pycnarmon discerptalis" OR "eggplant fruit borer" OR "brinjal fruit borer" OR "foreuse des solanées" OR "Auberginenfruchtbohrer" OR "brinjal fruit and shoot borer" OR "eggplant fruit and shoot borer" OR "Foreuse des solanées")	897

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates.

3.2 Document screening

Document screening was performed using the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2022) and followed a two-step approach: Title and Abstract (TIAB), and Full Text screening. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question "*Is this reference relevant for the QPRA?*". The first step was based on the title and abstract and the above question was applied to discriminate between relevant, irrelevant, and unclear references. A reference was considered relevant if it contained information on Pest Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and/or its Impact. By selecting the answer "Yes" (Figure 1), the reference was automatically moved to the next screening level (i.e., full text). When from the abstract it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the "Unclear" option was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening was based on the full text of the documents that passed the first step and an *ad hoc* questionnaire, divided in seven sections (Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Spread, and Impact) was used to facilitate the extraction of data and information.

Reference Details

RefID: 8, Use of intercrops and antifeedants for management of eggplant shoot and fruit borer *Leucinodes orbonalis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae)
Satpathy, S., Mishra, D. S.

Attachments
PDF - Satpathy-2011-Use of intercrops and antifeedan.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)

Full Text Links
DOI.org

Reference Label(s):
Leucinodes

The impact of vegetational diversity through intercrop and the application of antifeedants were assessed for their ability to reduce the infestation of shoot and fruit borer *Leucinodes orbonalis* Guen. on eggplant. Intercropping with coriander and fennel reduced the fruit damage to 12-15% compared with the plots with eggplant monoculture. Total yield of intercropped eggplant was significantly higher than the eggplant monoculture yield. Coriander and fennel were found to be equally effective in reducing infestation by *L. orbonalis*. Neem seed kernel extract (4%) and the neem-based product Neemarin(R) were found to be more effective in controlling *L. orbonalis* than ash dust and were lower than the untreated control. The fruit infestation level in the neem treatments (either of them) was 15-16% less than the untreated check. The interaction of intercrop and antifeedant showed that coriander-intercropped eggplant along with foliar spray of Neemarin(R) significantly reduced fruit damage. In a multiple choice chamber, orientation of female moths to eggplant was significantly reduced in the presence of fennel or coriander. With 38.9 and 37.1 per female, the extent of egg-laying by *L. orbonalis* on eggplant associated with fennel or coriander, respectively, was significantly less than on sole eggplant (48.4/female).

Try New Review Screen (Beta) NEW!

Submit Form and go to This Form - Next Reference or Skip to Next

1. Is this reference relevant for the QPRA?
Yes No Unclear

Clear Response

Figure 1. Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.43. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed Jan-Sep 2023. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>).

3.2.1 Data extraction

Data extraction was also performed in DistillerSR for the documents passing the full-text screening.

Table 3: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file.

Field name	Description	Type
Refid	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
Reference	Full reference for the record	String
Source type	Categorises the type of reference. Available options: original study, review study, distribution map, other	String
Distribution	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Physiology_Ecology	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
T	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
RH	Presence of information on humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Photoperiod	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Host	Presence of information on host availability (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Biology	Presence of information on pest biology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Impact	Presence of information on the impact of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

<i>Spread</i>	Presence of information on the spread of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Control Methods</i>	Presence of information on control methods used against the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

A Master File was developed containing a summary of the information (**Error! Reference source not found.**) contained in each reference. Seven independent tables on each of the topics relevant for the QPRA were developed: Pest Distribution, Host list, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and Impact. **Error! Reference source not found.** includes an explanation of the fields present in each of the independent tables.

3.2.2 Köppen–Geiger climate classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (EFSA & Maiorano, 2022) was used to develop climate suitability maps based on the climate classification approach. The Köppen–Geiger climate classification from Kottek et al. (2006) after the re-analysis of Rubel et al. (2017), based on the period 1986–2010 (available at <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>), was used. The climate types present in the observed locations of *L. orbonalis* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are also present in Europe.

3.2.3 Degree-days and number of generations maps

Degree-days and number of generations maps were developed for South-East Asia (main area of distribution of *L. orbonalis*), and Europe and the Mediterranean basin.

Degree-days were calculated by accumulating the positive differences between the daily mean temperature and a base temperature (*BaseT*) of 15°C. If daily mean temperature was below *BaseT*, that day did not contribute to temperature accumulation. A linear regression model based on data from Dhaliwal and Aggarwal (2021) (Dhaliwal & Aggarwal, 2021; Islam, Roknuzzaman, Hassan, & Ullah, 2020) was used to estimate the number of degree days to complete one generation, i.e. 438.6 accumulated degree-days. Degree-days were calculated using the Copernicus ERA5-Land data (Muñoz Sabater, 2019) for the 30 years period 1993-2022.

3.2.4 Species distribution modelling (SDM)

The suitability of the EU territory to the establishment of *L. orbonalis* was analysed using a species distribution model (SDM) ensemble developed in RStudio (RStudio Team) using the R *sdm* package (Naimi & Araújo, 2016). The bioclimatic variables from WorldClim (**Error! Reference source not found.**), for the period 1970-2000, at the resolution of 10 arcmin (i.e. ~ 18km x 18km), were used as predictor variables (Fick & Hijmans, 2017)⁴.

Only pest distribution observations at the point level (see Figure 4) were used in the analysis as presence-only data. These were thinned to include only one random location in each grid cell of the distribution area, still with the same resolution of 10 arcminutes. The area for the training of the SDM models was between the geographical bounding-box 40°E and 165°E, 10°S and 45°N.

Pseudo-absence data were generated inside the training area with two approaches (**Error! Reference source not found.**). In the first approach, the Panel assumed a presence zone for

⁴ Available at <https://www.worldclim.org/data/worldclim21.html>

L. orbonalis through both the observations at the point and at the administrative unit (FAO GAUL 0, 1, and 2) levels in South-East Asia, and the organism's natural dispersal capacity (in the order of 10 km for an adult). Therefore, a modified convex hull was created and used as exclusion area for pseudo-absence points. In creating the convex hull, large part of the Chinese province of Yunnan was excluded from the exclusion area because of the presence of high mountains, not considered suitable for the organism by the Panel. In the second approach, pseudo-absences were created in the entire training area, with the only limitation of a buffer of 10 km around each distribution point.

For the convex-hull approach, three series of simulations were run based on different number of pseudoabsence points: 4800 pseudoabsence points (10x number of observations), 2400 (5x), and 480 (1x) random points. Since collinearity may arise among the predictors, the variance inflation factor (VIF) method was used to exclude all the Bioclimatic variables with collinearity. Then, the species distribution modelling methods were fitted to the predictor variables (Table 4).

Figure 2. Different approaches used for the generation of pseudoabsence data.

Ten models have been used to fit the data: *bioclim*, *brt*, *cart*, *dismo*, *gam*, *mars*, *maxent*, *rf*, *rpart*, and *svm*. Data splitting was achieved through a five-fold cross validation process repeated for five times. Therefore, twenty-five simulations per model were created, yielding a total of 250 model runs. Ensemble modelling of the 250 simulations, based on the weighted average of the True Skill Statistics (TSS), was used to produce the final output.

Table 4: Bioclimatic variables from WorldClim (Fick and Hijmans, 2017).

Field name	Description
BIO1*	Annual Mean Temperature
BIO2	Mean Diurnal Range (Mean of monthly (max temp - min temp))
BIO3	Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (×100)
BIO4*	Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation ×100)
BIO5*	Max Temperature of Warmest Month
BIO6*	Min Temperature of Coldest Month
BIO7*	Temperature Annual Range (BIO5-BIO6)
BIO8	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter
BIO9	Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter
BIO10*	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter
BIO11*	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter
BIO12*	Annual Precipitation
BIO13	Precipitation of Wettest Month
BIO14*	Precipitation of Driest Month
BIO15	Precipitation Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation)
BIO16*	Precipitation of Wettest Quarter
BIO17	Precipitation of Driest Quarter
BIO18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter
BIO19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter

* Bioclimatic variables excluded due to collinearity

3.2.5 CLIMEX

The CLIMEX model (version 4.1.0.0, Kriticos et al., 2015) was also used to investigate the climate suitability of the EU to the establishment of *L. orbonalis*. Simulations were run using the climate dataset CM30 1995H V2 WO (Kriticos et al., 2012), package v4.1 (available at: <https://www.climond.org/>) to calculate the CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI). The parameterization (Table 5) of the indices influencing growth, heat and wet stresses was done using information from the literature and iterating simulations to fit the distribution data. The cold and dry stresses were parameterized using the CLIMEX genetic algorithm.

Table 5. CLIMEX parameterization. The values used were derived from the literature, modified through model iterations to fit the distribution data, and calculated using the CLIMEX genetic algorithm.

Class	Parameter	Description	No Moisture Index	Moisture Index	Source
Moisture index	SM0	Lower soil moisture threshold	-	0.01	Iteration
	SM1	Lower optimal soil moisture	-	0.1	Iteration
	SM2	Upper optimal soil moisture	-	3	Iteration
	SM3	Upper soil moisture threshold	-	4	Iteration
Temperature index	DV0	Lower temperature threshold	15°C	15°C	315
	DV1	Lower optimal temperature	26°C	26°C	24, 315, 1861
	DV2	Upper optimal temperature	38°C	38°C	24, 315, 1833
	DV3	Upper temperature threshold	39°C	39°C	1683
Cold stress	TTCS*	Cold stress temperature threshold	5.13°C	5.13°C	*
	THCS*	Cold stress accumulation rate	-0.00237 week ⁻¹	-0.00237 week ⁻¹	*
	DTCS	Cold stress will begin to accumulate when this threshold number of degree-days above DVCS is not achieved.	2°C	2°C	Iteration
	DHCS	Rate at which Cold Stress accumulates once the threshold number of degree-days above DVCS (DTCS) is not achieved	-0.001 week ⁻¹	-0.001 week ⁻¹	
	TTCSA	Average weekly temperature below which Cold Stress accumulates.	0°C	0°C	
	THCSA	Rate at which Cold Stress accumulates once temperatures drop below the threshold value of TTCS1.	0°C	0°C	
Heat stress	TTHS	Heat stress temperature threshold	39°C	39°C	1683
	THHS	Heat stress accumulation rate	0.001 week ⁻¹	0.001 week ⁻¹	
	DTHS	Heat stress will begin to accumulate when this threshold number of degree-days above DV3 is exceeded.	0°C	0°C	
	DHHS	This is the rate at which Heat Stress accumulates once the threshold number of degree-days above DV3 (DTHS) is exceeded	0°C	0°C	
Dry stress	SMDS*	Dry stress soil moisture value	0.09797	0.09797	*
	HDS*	Dry stress soil moisture rate	-0.00782 week ⁻¹	-0.00782 week ⁻¹	*
Wet stress	SMWS	Soil moisture wet stress threshold	4	4	Iteration
	HDS	Wet stress accumulation rate	0.001 week ⁻¹	0.001 week ⁻¹	
DD above DV0	DV0	Lower temperature threshold	15°C	15°C	315
	DV3	Upper temperature threshold	39°C	39°C	1683
DD above DVCS	DVCS*	Degree-days based cold stress	5.13°C	5.13°C	*
DD above DVHS	DVHS	Degree-days based heat stress	39°C	39°C	1683
Annual Heat sum	PDD**	Minimum degree day sum needed to complete a generation	438.6	438.6	**

* Values retrieved using the built-in CLIMEX genetic algorithm (version 4.1.0.0, Kriticos et al., 2015).

** PDD was calculated with a linear regression model using life table studies data (see section: Degree-days and number of generations maps).

4 Results

4.1 Systematic literature review

The PRISMA diagram (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, Altman, & PRISMA Group*, 2009) in Figure 3 summarizes the results of the systematic literature search. A total of 2343 documents were found through Web of Science and Scopus. After deduplication in EndNote, 2045 were imported to DistillerSR. Eleven additional references found in Google Scholar and other sources provided by the Panel experts were included and a total number of 2056 references underwent the TIAB screening. Of these, 901 references were excluded because they did not contain relevant information, and the remaining 1155 were passed to the Full text screening. Data extraction was performed for 573 references while the remaining 582 were not analysed due to time constraint and repetition of already collected information. Therefore, 573 references constituted the sources for the present analysis. In 334 of these records data on pest distribution was extracted, 459 contained details on the hosts, 64 about physio-ecology of the pest, 183 concerned its biology, 303 the impact, 27 the spread, and 373 the control methods.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Name of the Pest:
Date of the search:
Literature Search String:

Figure 3. PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the distribution, hosts, physio-ecology, biology, impact, spread, and control methods of the pest *Leucinodes orbonalis*.

4.2 Observed pest distribution

The literature search yielded 734 records of observation at both point locations (coordinates) and administrative unit level. All the records are available in the observations file and shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** 4. From the observed distribution, 480 are point locations, reporting specific coordinates or relatively small administrative units (e.g., Indian counties) for which either the coordinates indicated in the paper or the coordinates from Google

Earth (<https://earth.google.com/web/>) were used. The remaining 255 observations are administrative units (e.g., countries, regions) identified through their FAO Global Administrative Unit Layer (GAUL) codes (https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/FAO_GAUL_2015_level1).

Figure 4. Known global distribution of *Leucinodes orbonalis*.

4.3 Köppen–Geiger climate matching

Figure 5. Köppen-Geiger climate matching for *Leucinodes orbonalis*. Only climates present in the EU and relevant for the organism were mapped.

4.4 Degree days and number of generations

A linear regression model was used to calculate the degree days required to complete one generation. This was calculated as the average of the calculated degree days to complete development at each constant temperature used in the experiment of Dhaliwal and Aggarwal (2021) to rear the organism.

Data source: ERA5-Land, Muñoz Sabater, J., (2019) was downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (2022). The results contain modified Copernicus Climate Change Service Information 1993-2022. Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may be made of the Copernicus information or data it contains.

Figure 6. Mean degree days accumulation for *Leucinodes orbonalis* in Europe and the Mediterranean Basin (1) and South-East Asia and India (2) based on a base temperature of 15°C. Degree-days were calculated for each year in the period 1993-2022 and then averaged.

Data source: ERA5-Land, Muñoz Sabater, J., (2019) was downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (2022). The results contain modified Copernicus Climate Change Service information 1993-2022. Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may be made of the Copernicus information or data it contains.

Figure 7. Estimated mean number of generations for *Leucinodes orbonalis* in Europe and the Mediterranean Basin (1) and South-East Asia and India (2). Number of generations were calculated considering a minimum number of accumulated degree days to complete one generation of 438.6 degree-days. Number of generations were calculated for each year in the period 1993-2022 and then averaged.

Data source: ERA5-Land, Muñoz Sabater, J., (2019) was downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (2022). The results contain modified Copernicus Climate Change Service information 1993-2022. Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may

Figure 8. Mean degree days accumulation in India and neighbouring regions.

Data source: ERA5-Land, Muñoz Sabater, J., (2019) was downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (2022). The results contain modified Copernicus Climate Change Service information 1993-2022. Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may be made of the Copernicus information or data it contains.

Figure 9. Estimated mean number of *Leucinodes orbonalis* generations in India and neighbouring regions.

4.5 CLIMEX

Figure 10. CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index for *Leucinodes orbonalis*. Figures A1 and A2 shows the results without including the calculation of the Moisture Index. Figure B1 and B2 shows the results including in the simulation the calculation of the Moisture Index.

4.6 Species distribution modelling

Figure 11. Climate suitability according to the species distribution model ensemble for India and Southeast Asia, and Europe and the Mediterranean basin. The pink polygon is the modified convex hull. Three different series of results are shown based on the number of random background points used for the simulations.

Figure 12. Climate suitability according to the SDM ensemble for India and Southeast Asia, and Europe and the Mediterranean basin. Background pseudoabsence points used for the SDM simulations were randomly generated in the entire training area (top figure).

5 Content of the *Leucinodes orbonalis* Zenodo repository

Leucinodes_orbonalis_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf

The file contains the methodology and results of the Climate Suitability Analysis for *L. orbonalis*, describing the extensive literature search and the climate classification. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Maps illustrate the pest distribution and the results of the climate suitability analyses. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2023) for an exhaustive and detailed discussion of the results.

Leucinodes_orbonalis_ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in *Leucinodes_orbonalis_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf*.

Leucinodes_orbonalis_ANNEX_B_Observations.csv

The file contains the observed distribution at a global level. Both punctual locations and administrative units are included.

Maps in .jpeg format

- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_Distribution.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_CLIMEX.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_KG.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_Mean_degree_days.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_generations.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_India_degree_days.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_India_generations.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_SDM_All_background_points_EU_Asia.jpeg*
- *Leucinodes_orbonalis_SDM_buffer.jpeg*

Leucinodes_orbonalis_PRA.gpkg

GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

Leucinodes_orbonalis_qgis_styles.zip

QGIS styles to replicate the symbology used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in *Leucinodes_orbonalis_PRA.gpkg*

References

- Dhaliwal, N. K., & Aggarwal, N. (2021). Development and survival of brinjal shoot and fruit borer *Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenee (Crambidae: Lepidoptera) at constant and alternating temperatures. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, *41*, 1717-1728.
- EFSA, & Maiorano, A. (2022). SCAN-Clim: a tool to support pest climate suitability analysis based on climate classification. *EFSA journal*, *20*(2), e07104.
- EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), Bragard C, Baptista P, Chatzivassiliou E, Di Serio F, Gonthier P, Jaques Miret JA, Justesen AF, MacLeod A, Magnusson CS, Milonas P, Navas-Cortes JA, Parnell S, Potting R, Reignault PL, Stefani E, Thulke H-H, Vicent Civera A, Yuen J, Zappala L, Mally R, Czwienczek E, Gobbi A, Lopez-Mercadal J, Maiorano A, Mosbach-Schulz O, Pautasso M, Rossi E, Stancanelli G, Tramontini S and Van der Werf W, 2023. Scientific Opinion on the pest risk assessment of *Leucinodes orbonalis* the European Union. EFSA Journal in preparation
- Evidence Partners. (2022). DistillerSR (Version 2.35): Distiller Inc.
- Fick, S. E., & Hijmans, R. J. (2017). WorldClim 2: new 1-km spatial resolution climate surfaces for global land areas. *International Journal of Climatology*, *37*(12), 4302-4315. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5086>
- Islam, T., Roknuzzaman, A., Hassan, K., & Ullah, M. S. (2020). Temperature impacts on the eggplant shoot and fruit borer *Leucinodes orbonalis*: a life table approach. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, *40*, 351-360.
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & PRISMA Group*, t. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *Annals of internal medicine*, *151*(4), 264-269.
- Muñoz Sabater, J. (2019). ERA5-Land hourly data from 1950 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). DOI: 10.24381/cds.e2161bac.
- Naimi, B., & Araújo, M. B. (2016). sdm: a reproducible and extensible R platform for species distribution modelling. *Ecography*, *39*(4), 368-375.
- RStudio Team. RStudio: Integrated Development for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA. Retrieved from <http://www.rstudio.com/>